

Momentum-Position Uncertainty Principle

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The momentum-position uncertainty principle $\Delta p \Delta x \geq \hbar/2$ is often derived in texts using Heisenberg's heuristic approach or a calculation based on the commutator of p and x together with Schwartz's inequality (or other operators, although such an approach does not hold for E and t). Δx and Δp are square roots of variances of x and p . For example, $\int dx x^2 W(x)W(x)$ is used in the one dimensional calculation of a bound wavefunction $W(x)$, where $W(x)W(x) = P(x)$. From the point of view of statistics, this appears completely normal, but we argue quantum mechanics is based on a wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. x^2 may be expanded as a Fourier series and interacts with $W(x)$ like a potential - in fact like the oscillator potential. Thus, we argue one may obtain the x, p uncertainty principle by using ideas from the harmonic oscillator ground state. Interestingly, the oscillator ground state has momentum and spatial wavefunctions of the same form as the classical statistical mechanical density and $\langle v \rangle \langle v \rangle$ has a similar x dependence as $\langle v^2 \rangle$ which usually does not occur.

Measurements in Quantum Mechanics

Quantum spatial density is given by $W(x)W(x)$ for a bound state which in turn is composed of $a(p_1) \exp(ip_1 x) + a(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x)$ summands. In a previous note, we argued that $a(p_1) \exp(ip_1 x)$ is the relative conditional probability for a particle to have p_1 at x at t_1 and $a(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x)$ and for it to have p_2 a tiny time later due to a stochastic hit. It is the product probability which we argue is key in quantum mechanics. If one wishes to perform a measurement of state $|W\rangle$ one may use $|W\rangle \langle W|$. Thus: $W(x)W(x) |W\rangle \langle W| = W(x) \langle W | W \rangle W(x) = W(x)W(x)$.

In general, a wavefunction may interact with a potential with both being written as Fourier series i.e. $V(x)W(x) = \sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx) a(p) \exp(ipx)$. This, in turn, is equivalent to: $\sum_i b(i) |W_i(x)\rangle$ where $W_i(x)$ is some basis. Like above, it is the product probability one seeks, because one may have a component $d(p_1) \exp(ip_1 x)$ at one instant and $d(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x)$ a tiny time later. Thus, $V(x)W(x) V(x)W(x)$ is used.

If the measurement seeks state $|W_1(x)\rangle$ (for example), one uses $|W_1\rangle \langle W_1|$ just as in the spatial density case. Then the probability to find state W_1 is:

$$\langle W_1 | V | W \rangle \langle W | V | W_1 \rangle \text{ where } W_1 \text{ and } W \text{ are real (in this example)} \quad ((1))$$

Just as one breaks $V(x)$ into a Fourier series, averages of other functions of x such as x^2 in a variance calculation may also be expressed as a Fourier series and interpreted as a potential because they interact with the wavefunction $W(x)$. We argue that $\int W(x)W(x) x^2 dx$ with $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ which is common in statistics may have a different interpretation in quantum mechanics. The Fourier series terms of x^2 interacts with $W(x)$ exactly like the oscillator potential. We argue this idea may be used to calculate the p - x uncertainty relationship.

P-X Uncertainty Expression Based on the Quantum Oscillator

The p-x uncertainty relationship is: $\Delta x \Delta p \geq \hbar/2$ where Δ is the square root of the variance. For $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ real, we argue that $\int dx W(x)W(x) x=0$ and $\int dp a(p)a(p) p =0$. If $W(x)$ is real, then $a(p)= \int dx W(x) \exp(ipx) x$ which coupled with $a(-p)$ leads to the imaginary term cancelling. As a result, one must first calculate:

$$A = \int dx x^2 W(x)W(x) \quad \text{and} \quad B = \int dp p^2 a(p)a(p) \quad ((2))$$

These, however, are main ingredients of the average potential and kinetic energy calculations of an oscillator for which $E = \hbar \omega (n + .5)$ with $n=0$ being the lowest state:

$A = .5k B = .5/m = \text{Average KE} = \text{Average PE}$ but $\text{Average KE} = \text{Average PE} = .25 \omega$ for the gs oscillator. For all higher oscillator states average KE = average PE, but values are higher so for the oscillator:

$$AB = .25 k/m \geq \hbar \hbar \sqrt{k/m} \sqrt{k/m} = .25 \hbar^2 \quad \text{or} \quad AB \geq .25 / (mm) \hbar \hbar$$

Taking the square root yields:

$$\Delta p \Delta x \geq .5 \hbar \quad \text{for an oscillator.}$$

For a non-oscillator wavefunction:

$W(x) = \sum_i d(i) W_i(x)$ where W_i is an oscillator wavefunction where $d(i)$ is a number.

$W(x)$ is therefore sum of various oscillator states, but it is also normalized:

$$\int dx W(x)W(x) = 1$$

One may guess, therefore, that the expectation values of $.5kx^2$ and $-1/2m d/dx d/dx$ for such a superposition should both be greater than than the ground state case. Physically, one may start with the ground state and add energy to excite it into the superposition arrangement of $W(x)$. It seems such a scenario should have more average potential and kinetic energy as each excited state has more average kinetic and potential energy than the ground state. $.5kx^2$ and $1/2m p^2$ are unique to the oscillator in that they represent the potential and kinetic energies. If one tried to write W_0 (the oscillator in terms of $\sum Y_i$ where Y_i is another basis, $.5kx^2$ and $1/2m p^2$ would represent kinetic and potential energy in that basis.

Then, one may suggest that:

$$\Delta x \Delta p \geq \hbar/2 \quad \text{for all bound wavefunctions} \quad ((3))$$

It should be noted that $1/2m \langle p^2 \rangle$ is the average kinetic energy in any system and $\langle p \rangle = 0$. Thus, the variance of p is really related to the rms average velocity in a system or the square root of

average kinetic energy. Thought of in this way, one would not necessarily associate it with resolution of momentum. Another way to consider this is:

$KE(x) = [\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^*p/2m \ \exp(ipx)] / W(x)$
 And the probability to be at x is $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ so:

$$N = KE(x)P(x) = W(x)[\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^*p/2m \ \exp(ipx)]$$

which is related to the variance squared of p using $P(p/x)$ with the second piece being:

$$M = [\text{Integral } dx \ P(x)/W \ (-dW/dx)] [\text{Integral } dx \ P(x)/W \ (dW/dx)] = 0 \quad (4)$$

So the variance squared is proportional to $KE(x)P(x)$ or $\langle p^*p \rangle$. This is an average variance squared at each x weighted by $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$, but it is proportional to the average kinetic energy in the system. Either interpretation should be useful. Using $P(p/x)$ one may calculate variance squared at a particular x and not really worry about the integral over x .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue the momentum-position uncertainty condition seems to follow from properties of the ground state oscillator which yields an equality. All other wavefunctions then result in $\Delta > \hbar/2$. We also argue that $\langle p^*p \rangle$ is related to average kinetic energy for all wavefunctions while $\langle x^*x \rangle$ is the expectation of the oscillator potential.